

Aim

NFDI4Microbiota aims to steadily improve its services through gathering community feedback. For this purpose the consortium has implemented community feedback from various channels, such as the scientific advisory board (SAB), questionnaires and workshops. In the current report for 2022, NFDI4Microbiota has collected and analyzed feedback from helpdesk requests, community workshops, the ambassador program and questionnaires.

Feedback from the fifth community workshop

During the fifth (virtual) community workshop on 18th of March 2022, the consortium presented the mission and work progress of NFDI4Microbiota and launched the ambassador program. Participants had the opportunity to ask and discuss questions in small groups and to note down their wishes and ideas on a digital whiteboard. Below is an overview of the main needs.

- **Training courses and information material:**

There is a general desire for more workshops, courses and webinars to be delivered online or in a hybrid format. In addition, training events should be recorded in order to provide training and information material on the web portal for self-directed learning. There is a common need for training and information on the following topics:

- o Data transformations for multi-omics data
- o Setup of RNA-seq experiments and analysis
- o Hands on training to handle metadata
- o Metatranscriptomics data analysis
- o Example submissions to repositories
- o How to set up experiments
- o Collaborative writing with integrated data analysis (rmarkdown, jupyter)
- o Course on using R

NFDI4Microbiota already offers different types of training events (e.g. face-to-face or online, workshops or summer schools). If available, the teaching material is provided as Open Educational Resources (OER) published on Zenodo with an open license (e.g. CC-BY, CC0) and then linked on the web portal. In addition, training events are recorded and the videos put online. NFDI4Microbiota training events already cover different scopes and different levels of details, and in addition the consortium plans to offer train-the-trainer workshops. Future scopes covered will include general issues of research data management (RDM), data quality, bioinformatics and cloud accessibility, as well as microbiology-specific courses (e.g. microbial analyses, metagenomics, proteomics).

- **Web portal:**

The community asked for more information and access to Use Cases provided through the NFDI4Microbiota web portal. This was realized in August 2022 when a new version of the web portal was implemented. Active Use Cases are now described in more detail and a list of frequently asked questions about Use Cases is available. Moreover, graphical abstracts will be added in 2023.

- **Data and metadata:**

There is a general need for support to help research communities submit data and metadata of good quality. This includes frictionless data submission to repositories such as European Bioinformatic Institute (EBI, <https://www.ebi.ac.uk>), for example through a containerized data submission tool with built-in validation, and a clear description of the

required metadata. The community also likes to see the establishment of metadata quality control and standardization, provision of metadata templates for repositories and asks for help with data annotation and submission through data managers and tutorials. This can be achieved through a standardised data storage option, which allows sharing of and searching for data sets. NFDI4Microbiota addresses these challenges by facilitating and stimulating the sharing and re-use of data by supporting easy and open access to microbial and associated data following the FAIR principles. Commonly used data and metadata standards have been identified and / or are being discussed with international partners and the consortium will establish an online system to check data quality and metadata standards. The workflows provided by NFDI4Microbiota will generate data in a form that can be easily deposited in public repositories. The output of these analysis pipelines will be of a standard format and contain relevant metadata. Moreover, a scalable and easily accessible domain-agnostic data storage platform for storing and sharing datasets intermediately before final submission to commonly used data repositories is being developed. In addition, the consortium will support high-quality research data management by introducing professional data stewards into the microbiological research process.

- **Outreach:**

To raise awareness of the work of NFDI4Microbiota, the community likes to see poster presentations and stands at microbiology conferences. NFDI4Microbiota's target audience includes a diverse set of microbiology-related and application-related communities of e.g. bacteriologists, virologists, clinician scientists, epidemiologists, parasitologists, mycologists and microbial ecologists who focus on clinical, environmental, agricultural and biotechnological applications. To reach the individual groups, the consortium is present at important community conferences every year, such as the Annual Meeting of the German Society for Hygiene and Microbiology (DGHM) and Association for General and Applied Microbiology (VAAM), the Annual Meeting of the Society for Virology, International Virus Bioinformatics Meeting (EVBC), the DGEpi Jahrestagung for epidemiologists and the Annual Meeting of the German Society for Parasitology. In addition, the consortium also wants to present itself at other events that specialise in biotechnology, agriculture, clinical research, environment and ecology, for example. NFDI4Microbiota plans to present posters on those events or provide an information booth to promote the topics and enable direct contact with consortium representatives and discussion of needs.

Feedback from ambassadors

The connection and interaction with the German microbiology community is the key for the success of NFDI4Microbiota and the goal of its ambassador program. The ambassadors help to efficiently assess and communicate the needs of their community and the consortium provides suitable solutions. Presentations on different topics and a bilateral exchange with the ambassadors take place during the monthly Coffee Talk series. In this setting the community, represented by the ambassadors, can ask questions and present their problems, which will be addressed by the consortium, if possible.

Community requests via the NFDI4Microbiota helpdesk

NFDI4Microbiota has established a helpdesk (contact form on the web portal) to offer a broad spectrum of support to overcome individual problems faced by researchers. This includes the writing of data management plans, data submission, metadata collection and legal issues (e.g. data licenses). In 2022, the helpdesk team counted 14 requests regarding the following topics: software (1), training (4), ambassador program (1), research data management (1), participation (3), use cases (2), and others (2). All enquirers could be answered and reviewing the requests helps the consortium to improve services and procedures as well as to compile a catalog of frequently asked questions.

Questionnaires

- **Survey on the use of Electronic Lab Notebooks**

Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs) play an important role in documenting research data: they provide clear documentation of experiment planning and implementation and of data generation and processing. One of the aims of NFDI4Microbiota is to ensure research data is captured as early in the process as possible in order to feed it directly into the analysis pipeline. The consortium conducted a survey on the use of ELNs which was intended for NFDI4Microbiota partners and participants. Its goal was to understand why or why not researchers use an ELN, and what are/were their hurdles in implementing or using an ELN. Only around 26% of respondents currently use an ELN indicating a clear need to build awareness. Moreover, the ELNs being used vary greatly and are in need of improvements. To further support the use of ELNs and identify the needs of the community, NFDI4Microbiota organized a workshop in February, 2023. Ultimately, the consortium would like to recommend a single ELN and guide researchers in the selection and implementation of the appropriate ELN for their research.